

A STUDY ON INTERNATIONAL BRAND ICE CREAM IN INDIAN MARKET SPECIAL REFERENCE TO COIMBATORE

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Abstract:

The brand awareness place a big role in influencing the customers purchase decision. Best marketing and brand awareness activity in current scenario is advertisement therefore effective advertisement should be made to attract more customers. In Indian ice cream industry where switching cost is negligible a product can't be placed in the market on the basis of brand alone, but it should match the spending power of the customers and cordial relationship. The manager of the outlet has to adopt various marketing strategies in order to gain brand reputation and to retain their customers by providing quality products and services.

Key Words: Advertisement, Customer & Marketing Strategies

Introduction:

Ice cream is a sweetened frozen food typically eaten as a snack or dessert. It is usually made from dairy products, such as milk and cream, and often combined with fruits or other ingredients and flavours. It is typically sweetened with sucrose, corn syrup, cane sugar, beet sugar, and/or other sweeteners. Typically, flavourings and colourings are added in addition to stabilizers. The mixture is stirred to incorporate air spaces and cooled below the freezing point of water to prevent detectable ice crystals from forming. The result is smooth, semi-solid foam that is solid at very low temperatures. Ice cream was made by hand in a large bowl placed inside a tub filled with ice and salt. This was called the pot-freezer method. French confectioners refined the pot-freezer method, making ice cream in a sorbetière (a covered pail with a handle attached to the lid). In the pot-freezer method, the temperature of the ingredients is reduced by the mixture of crushed ice and salt. The salt water is cooled by the ice, and the action of the salt on the ice causes it to (partially) melt, absorbing latent heat and bringing the mixture below the freezing point of pure water. The immersed container can also make better thermal contact with the salty water and ice mixture than it could with ice alone.

Statement of the Problem:

With so many players in the market with little differentiation, the market is facing the issue of commoditisation. Flavour, taste, quality and Branding are the major differentiation opportunities in this industry. Flavour and product varieties were the route taken by major players. But flavours/varieties can be easily replicated by the competitors. Hence the only meaningful differentiation could be the brand. The availability of branded ice cream outlets are increasing rapidly, an attempt is made to learn which branded ice cream outlet is most popularly visited by the customers. Various branded companies compete with each other to provide similar features yet at the same time they are distinguished by their flavours, colour, design and service. This made the research to find out the reason why the customers prefer particular branded ice cream outlet. Therefore this is identified as the problem of the study on customers preference towards various branded ice cream outlets in Coimbatore city.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To study the factors influencing the customer to purchase the ice cream from the branded outlets.
- ✓ To study the source of awareness of the respondents towards various branded outlets.
- ✓ To analyze the pattern of purchase of ice cream from the branded ice cream outlets.
- ✓ To analyze the level of satisfaction of customers towards branded ice cream in the branded outlets.

Research Methodology:

A research design is the overall plan or program of research. A research design or model indicates a plan of action to be carried out in connection with a proposed research work.

Area of the Study:

The area of the study is Coimbatore city. It is popularly known as Manchester of south India, is situated in western part of the state of Tamil Nadu.

Sample Size:

The sample of 200 respondents was chosen for the study. 40 respondents from the each of the branded ice cream outlet were selected based on convenience sampling method. Five outlets were selected for the study namely boomerang, bon-bon, ibaco, baskin robins and kwality walls.

Data Sources:

Primary data have been used for the purpose of this study. The primary data have been collected in the form of questionnaire by issuing it to the general public who visits the branded ice cream outlets. The questions in the questionnaire were prepared in such a way that it will be easy for people to read and understand for filling it.

Tools for Analysis:

The data collected were analysed on parallel with the objectives of the study on hand.

Limitations of the Study:

The study is limited to 200 respondents only. These 200 respondents cannot represent the whole population in the Coimbatore city. Only 5 ice cream outlets in city where taken because of the time constraint.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

S.No	Gender	Respondents	
		Numbers	%
1	Male	115	57.5
2	Female	85	42.5
	Total	200	100

The above table shows that 57.5% of the respondents are male and 42.5% of the respondents are female.

AGE OF THE RESPONDENTS

S.No	Age	Respondents	
		Numbers	%
1	Less than 20 Yrs	81	40.5
2	21-30 Yrs	82	41
3	31-40 Yrs	27	13.5
4	Above 40 Yrs	10	5
	Total	200	100

The above table shows that 41% of the respondents are between 21-30 years of age, 40.5 % of the respondents are of the age group less than 20 years, 13.5% of the respondents are between 31-40 years of age and 5% of the respondents are above 40 years of age.

Marital Status of the Respondents:

S.No	Marital Status	Respondents	
		Numbers	%
1	Single	149	74.5
2	Married	51	25.5
	Total	200	100

The above table shows that 74.5 % of the respondents are single and 25.5% of the respondents are married.

Educational Qualification of the Respondents:

S.No	Educational Qualification	Respondents	
		Numbers	%
1	School Level	27	13.5
2	College Level	123	61.5
3	Professionals	48	24
4	Others	2	1
	Total	200	100

The above table shows that 61.5% of the respondents are at college level, 24% of the respondents are professionals, 13.5 % of the respondents are at school level, and 1% of the respondents are under the category of others which include respondents who have completed diploma.

Place of Residence of the Respondents:

S.No	Place of Residence	Respondents	
		Numbers	%
1	Rural	50	25
2	Urban	120	60
3	Semi Rural	30	15
	Total	200	100

The above table shows that 60% of the respondents are residing in urban areas, 25% of the respondents are residing in rural areas, and 15% of the respondents are residing in semi urban areas.

Findings:

- ✓ Majority (57.5 %) of the respondents are Male.

- ✓ Majority (41%) of the respondents are between the age group 21-30 years.
- ✓ Majority (74.5%) of the respondents are Single.
- ✓ Majority (61.5%) of the respondents are in college level
- ✓ Majority (60%) of the respondents are residing in urban area.
- ✓ Majority (55.5%) of the respondents are students
- ✓ Majority (30.5%) of the respondent's family monthly income is between `15000-`30000.
- ✓ Majority (70.5%) of the respondents are from nuclear family.
- ✓ Majority (56.5%) of the respondents have between 2-4 family members.
- ✓ Majority (48%) of the respondents have 2-4 kids in the family.
- ✓ Majority (68.5%) of the respondents buy ice cream from the branded outlets.
- ✓ Majority (36.5%) of the respondents are aware of the branded ice cream outlets through friends.
- ✓ Majority (37%) of the respondents have chosen television as the medium of awareness.
- ✓ Majority (28%) of the respondents most often visit the branded ice cream outlet Boomerang
- ✓ Majority (50%) of the respondents visit branded ice cream outlets with friends
- ✓ Majority (32%) of the respondents visit the branded ice cream outlets at weekends.
- ✓ Majority (47.5%) of the respondents visit the branded ice cream outlets in the evening.
- ✓ Majority (33%) of the respondents like to have in romantic atmosphere.
- ✓ Majority (29.5%) of the respondents like to buy scoops
- ✓ Majority (37%) of the respondents are attracted by the color of the package.
- ✓ Majority (42%) of the respondents prefer to have milkshake as an alternative to ice cream
- ✓ Majority (45.5%) of the respondents like to prefer takeaway services provided by the branded ice cream outlets
- ✓ Majority (49.5%) of the respondents spend between `100-`500 on a single purchase of ice cream
- ✓ Majority (78%) of the respondents are interested in the offers provided by branded ice cream outlets.
- ✓ Majority (41%) of the respondents prefers buy one get one offer from the branded ice cream outlet.
- ✓ Majority (29%) of the respondents prefer to have clean atmosphere in the branded ice cream outlet.

Suggestions:

- ✓ Quality of the Ice Cream: The flavors texture, melting quality of the ice cream can be improved in order to attract the customers.
- ✓ Cleanliness: Cleanliness is the important factor which a customer will observe before visiting the shop. The branded outlets would focus on cleanliness of the shop in order to attract the customers to visit their branded ice cream outlet.
- ✓ Alternatives: Alternatives like milkshake, sundae, coffee, cakes can be provided by the ice cream outlets as an alternative to the ice cream which will attract the customers to visit the branded outlets.
- ✓ Offers: Offers like buy one get one free, free toppings, discounts can be given to the customers which will make the customers to visit the shop regularly.
- ✓ Atmosphere: The outlets can emphasis on creating a romantic atmosphere to attract more youth.
- ✓ Frequency of Visit: Most of the customers visit the outlets in the weekend so outlets can provide special offers on weekend.

Conclusion:

The manager of the outlet has to adopt various marketing strategies in order to gain brand reputation and to retain their customers by providing quality products and services.

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